

CONSORT 2010

Manuscript: Therapeutic turricephaly for glioblastoma: randomised sham-controlled trial (XXL-GBM)

Authors: Stefano Natangelo; Lucia Cappellini [Fictional]; Daniel Skullridge [Fictional]

Journal target: Journal of Secondary Endpoints

Design: Multicentre, double-blind, sham-controlled randomised simulation (no human participants)

Section/Topic	Item No	Checklist item	Reported on page/section
Title and abstract	1a	Identification as a randomised trial in the title	Title: 'randomised sham-controlled trial (XXL-GBM)'
Title and abstract	1b	Structured summary of trial design, methods, results, and conclusions	Abstract (unstructured by journal style) summarises design, allocation, endpoints, and key results
Introduction	2a	Scientific background and explanation of rationale	Introduction: Monro-Kellie doctrine; container vs compartments rationale
Introduction	2b	Specific objectives or hypotheses	Introduction: hypothesis that planned cranial expansion delays pressure-driven deterioration
Methods: Trial design	3a	Description of trial design (such as parallel, factorial), including allocation ratio	Study design: parallel-group, 1:1 allocation; double-blind, sham-controlled
Methods: Trial design	3b	Important changes to methods after trial commencement (with reasons)	Not applicable (simulation; pre-specified plan)
Methods: Participants	4a	Eligibility criteria for participants	Participants: IDH-wt GBM, KPS \geq 70, midline

			shift ≤5 mm; HTPS exclusions [1]
Methods: Participants	4b	Settings and locations where the data were collected	Four tertiary neuro-oncology centres (simulated)
Methods: Interventions	5	The interventions for each group with sufficient details to allow replication	Interventions: +12% cranial dome (PEEK preferred) vs standard closure; peri-operative care harmonised [2,3]
Methods: Outcomes	6a	Completely defined pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures, including how and when they were assessed	Outcomes: primary ICP threshold time; secondary headache, steroids, PFSk, OS, adherence
Methods: Outcomes	6b	Any changes to trial outcomes after the trial commenced, with reasons	None (simulation)
Methods: Sample size	7a	How sample size was determined	Sample size: HR 0.67, 118 events, 80% power, $\alpha=0.05$; simulated n=150
Methods: Sample size	7b	When applicable, explanation of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines	None (simulation)
Methods: Randomisation—Sequence generation	8a	Method used to generate the random allocation sequence	Secure web system; permuted blocks; stratified by centre, MGMT, location
Methods: Randomisation—Type	8b	Type of randomisation; details of any restriction (such as	Blocked randomisation; stratified (details above)

			blocking and block size)	
Methods: Allocation concealment	9		Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence	Central web allocation; concealment maintained until assignment
Methods: Implementation	10		Who generated the random sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions	Central system generated sequence; local teams enrolled/assigned (simulation)
Methods: Blinding	11a		If done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions and how	Patients and outcomes assessors blinded; Trial Cap; mirror-free living; no scalp palpation; CNRP for reports [2]
Methods: Blinding	11b		If relevant, description of the similarity of interventions	Sham = standard closure; masking achieved behaviourally and via reporting policy (no filled dummy implant on ethics grounds)
Methods: Statistical methods	12a		Statistical methods used to compare groups for primary and secondary outcomes	Stratified Cox for time-to-event; linear mixed-effects for continuous outcomes
Methods: Statistical methods	12b		Methods for additional analyses, such as subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses	Pre-specified sensitivity excluding unblindings; no subgroup claims
Results: Participant flow	13a		For each group, the numbers of participants who	Flow: 150 randomised (75/75); primary ascertainment

		were randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and were analysed	148/150; see Figure 1 (CONSORT)
Results: Participant flow	13b	For each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons	Two withdrew before monitoring; documented protocol deviations (head-touch, cap-seal)
Results: Recruitment	14a	Dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up	Simulated timeline; follow-up to 6 months for primary endpoint
Results: Recruitment	14b	Why the trial ended or was stopped	Fixed simulation horizon
Results: Baseline data	15	Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group	Not shown (simulation); randomisation assumed balance
Results: Numbers analysed	16	Number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis	Intention-to-treat: all 150; two censored at time zero
Results: Outcomes and estimation	17a	For each primary and secondary outcome, results for each group, and the estimated effect size and its precision	Primary median 4.6 vs 3.1 months; HR 0.67 (95% CI 0.46–0.98), p=0.04; secondary outcomes as reported
Results: Outcomes and estimation	17b	For binary outcomes, presentation of both absolute and relative effect sizes is recommended	Not applicable (time-to-event primary)

Results: Ancillary analyses	18	Results of any other analyses performed, including subgroup analyses	Sensitivity excluding safety-driven unblindings; consistent
Results: Harms	19	All important harms or unintended effects	Safety: wound 4% vs 3%; rim pain 3%; dermatitis/pruritus 6%; cervical discomfort \geq G2 more frequent with dome; no MRI-related events [4–7]
Discussion	20	Trial limitations	All data simulated; implants fictional; masking challenges acknowledged
Discussion	21	Generalisability (external validity, applicability) of the trial findings	Conceptual/methodological implications; not clinical advocacy
Discussion	22	Interpretation consistent with results, balancing benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence	Delay in pressure-driven decline without survival gain; imaging/implant considerations [4–7]
Other information	23	Registration number and name of trial registry	Not applicable (simulation)
Other information	24	Where the full trial protocol can be accessed	Available on request as simulation notes
Other information	25	Sources of funding and other support; role of funders	Cappellini (Oversized Hats) Inc.; no role in design/analysis/writing